

IV: Preliminary Evidence for Quarks and Preons in Mirror Space-Time, and a New Approach to Unification*

R J Ellis[†]

Corpus Christi College (Alumnus), Oxford OX1 4JF, UK

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The nature of matter in mirror space-time, is investigated. Landau realised general relativity is incomplete because it does not correct for the Observer's reference frame. Chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR) predicts a second time dimension directed from the future to the past, in mirror space-time, and new phenomena at low energies. CIGR predicts that massive particles are dipoles, with the negative mass state being in mirror space-time. We investigate Ehrenhaft's (and other's) claims to have observed fractional electric charges, and Millikan's electron charge experiments, taking into account this new physics, *which allows a second type of charge quantisation*. We conclude that Ehrenhaft and others did observe fractional charges, in mirror space-time, and there is corroborating evidence for a few of these in Millikan's data. We explain these results in terms of different objectives, hardware, and the photo-mirror effect. We present evidence for fractional charges (mirror quarks and preons) in mirror space-time, produced by reversing the direction of time via the photo-mirror effect. The data rule out preon models with charges of $e/3$ and $2e/3$, but are compatible with charges of $e/9$. We conjecture that preons are dark matter.

Keywords: Chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR); fractional charges; unification; quarks and preons; dark matter; mirror space-time; photo-mirror effect.

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper is not about the claimed observation of fractional electric charges in normal 4D space-time. It is about the possible observation of fractional charges in mirror space-

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[†]*Email address:* r.ellis@physics.oxon.org

time. Therefore we need to define mirror space-time.

The concept of a mirror or dual universe is not new. One of the earliest came from the idea that parity could be conserved if there was a parallel hidden (mirror) sector.[1] In a slightly different approach Turok and his colleagues apply the CPT theorem to the Big Bang, thereby generating two universes.[2] Another approach involves a “mid-point” based on time-reversal-symmetric processes, which shows that a *Janus point* (looking both ways) develops. Barbour and his colleagues introduce the concept of *entaxy* from the Greek “towards order”, as opposed to entropy.[3] Another different approach is to use supersymmetry to bring duality into the standard model.[4] However these are new theories, which are not exactly the subject of this paper, because they do not explain peculiar experimental results, such as observation of magnetic monopoles and fractional electric charge (see below).

It is not well known that general relativity also predicts a dual universe,[5] but this does not fit the data either, at least not without extension. The problem is that these are, in the main, grandiose theories of dual universes on a macroscopic scale, whereas the data require a theory which predicts a dual structure for space-time on a small scale, which can be explored experimentally in the laboratory. In fact there is an extended version of general relativity which includes the Observer, which predicts *a second time dimension, and that space time is dual*. This new physics extends the low energy frontier of particle physics,[6] provides an explanation for the occasional observation of fractional charges, and opens up a new approach to unification (see below).

Another advantage of this approach is that it is based upon general relativity, which is already accepted as the correct theory of space-time. General relativity predicts a dynamical relationship between matter and space-time, which leads to the curvature of the latter. However, such effects are small (apart from gravity) and so they tend to be ignored, and space-time is seen as an arena in which particle interactions occur and are measured. Putting the Observer into general relativity changes all of that, as we shall see. This new physics is now presented in more detail to provide an overview of it.

1. In the 1930s, Landau and others realised that General Relativity does not correct for the reference frame of the Observer.[7] Different Observers may be in different reference frames with different gravitational fields, which may or may not be rotating. As a result, what is observed in a specific reference frame, is not well defined by the existing theory. *So without the Observer, General Relativity is incomplete.* Zelmanov developed the

strict mathematical formalism to calculate, for the general case, the observable values for any tensor quantity in 1944. However this was not published until 1956.[8, 9] These results were confirmed by Cattaneo.[10]

Physically observable quantities are obtained by projecting four-dimensional quantities onto the time lines and three-dimensional space of the Observers reference frame. Physically observable quantities must be invariant with respect to transformations of time, and so they are *chronometrically invariant quantities*. Borissova and Rabounski, have developed this theory further, and find that the chronometric invariant equations of motion for mass-bearing particles into the past and into the future, are asymmetric in time. They have shown that chronometric invariant general relativity (CIGR) predicts the existence of a second space-time, where time is directed from the future to the past.[11, 12] This mirror space-time occurs in space, but is separated from normal space-time by a threefold membrane. Therefore this extension of General Relativity is not in 4D (3,1), but 5 dimensions (3,2). It is thus a different theory and so we refer to it as “CIGR” until a more suitable name for it is chosen - see glossary. Our use of the word “mirror” is defined by this theory.

In CIGR, any mass-bearing particle has two time projections, one in each world (sector), and exists in two observable states. Each particle is in effect a four dimensional dipole object, which exists in two states: one in our world with positive mass and energy; the other in the mirror world with negative mass and energy. (NB this negative mass state is not anti-matter, because the inertial mass of anti-matter is positive.) However, these two states cannot “annihilate” or rather “nullify” (the net energy is zero) because they are separated by the membrane. Furthermore our world and the mirror world have the same background space, and *the three-dimensional momentum remains positive in both sectors*. [11, 12]

This second time dimension directed from the future to the past gives rise to new thermodynamics and other phenomena at ultra low (eV) energies. This extends the low energy frontier of particle physics,[6] *because space-time is dual*. A more detailed summary of this theory is presented here,[13] with some experimental evidence for magnetic monopoles in mirror space-time, and more detailed references. In effect the Universe has an “inside” and an “outside”, where normal experiments are done. So phenomena which occur in mirror space-time (i.e. on the inside) tend to be less objective than those in normal space-time, and therefore physicists have tended to reject them. We believe this

is an error.

2. The second little-known development was made by Brittin and Gamow who used the quantum theory of radiation to derive a simple theorem that solar photons can lower entropy levels at the earth's surface:[14]

$$\Delta S = \Delta S_s - \Delta S_e = \frac{4}{3} \Delta Q \left(\frac{1}{T_s} - \frac{1}{T_e} \right) \quad (1)$$

because of the temperature gradient $T_s > T_e > T_{\text{space}}$. This effect is also caused by visible photons from other sources. We originally investigated this experimentally, and found that the reduced entropy level occurs *and persists, contrary to the second law*. So we looked for an explanation and found it in CIGR. According to Eddington, entropy increases with the arrow of time.[15] So this process which lowers entropy levels, reverses the direction of time into that of mirror time. We have presented experimental evidence for this with more details here.[16]

3. The third little known phenomenon is the observation of magnetic monopoles at low energies, which many have rejected. When ferromagnetic particles are strongly illuminated, they move as magnetic monopoles. Ehrenhaft was the first to observe these in 1930 (before Dirac's paper.[17] However, despite being confirmed, these observations were very peculiar, because they stopped moving as monopoles when the illumination was turned off. *It was if they are not objectively real and so many rejected them..* Furthermore Dirac declared they could not be his monopoles because the force between two such monopoles was so great, they could only be separated at high energies. So they were ignored.

There the matter might have rested, but Mikhailov made repeated measurements on strongly illuminated ferromagnetic particles. He observed more than 1000 monopoles, and determined that the monopole charge is quantized ($g = n g_D$, $n = 1$ to 5) and $g = (0.99 \pm 0.05) g_D$ as predicted by Dirac.[18, 19] Mikhailov's experiments were done carefully, and so these results required an explanation, which is now outlined..

4. We combine together CIGR with the Brittin and Gamow Effect, to produce the photo-mirror hypothesis. According to this hypothesis, visible light switches the direction of time into that of mirror space-time, when the entropy level is reduced by means of the Brittin and Gamow effect.[13] However increases in the entropy level have the reverse effect:

$$normal(x, t) \quad dt/d\tau > 0 \quad \xleftrightarrow[\Delta S > 0]{\Delta S < 0} \quad dt/d\tau < 0 \quad mirror(x, -t) \quad (2)$$

We have presented evidence for this photo-mirror hypothesis, in experiments with light shining on water, so it is a real effect.[16] This photo-mirror effect explains the experiments on magnetic monopoles as follows. The intense illumination switches some or all of the ferromagnetic particles into mirror space-time, where the magnetic monopoles are revealed. In mirror-space time, these particles have negative mass, so that the strong attraction between two monopoles *will cause them to fly apart! So magnetic monopoles can be produced at low energies* using these methods, contrary to Dirac. Furthermore, the particles will cease to move as monopoles soon after the illumination is switched off, because the entropy will increase and space-time will revert back to the normal state according to equation 2.

Note that the experimental evidence for the photo-mirror effect is also preliminary evidence for unification, because the photo-mirror effect is based upon both general relativity (CIGR) and quantum mechanics (Brittin and Gamow effect). An interesting detail is that Mikhailov was able to observe particles with up to 5 Dirac monopole charges. This would not be possible if the magnetic monopoles were rare, but understandable if these monopoles are the negative poles of this matter in mirror space-time, which light can switch into.

5. In separate experiments, we have also presented evidence for a new type of (non-electromagnetic) radiation in sunlight which lowers entropy levels which persist.[20] We deduce that this new type of solar radiation is in the mirror sector because it produces ordered structures which persist. To summarize, we have thus found evidence for mirror space-time and its second time dimension,[16] also for new states of matter there (e.g. magnetic monopoles),[13] and for a new type of solar radiation, possibly a new force of nature.[20] Therefore the hypothesis is made that mirror space-time is the physical basis for the hidden sector of a new type of unified theory based upon CIGR and quantum mechanics, which has yet to be formulated mathematically.

These results provide examples of the new low energy phenomena which occur in mirror space-time beyond the standard model. Recently Oppenheim has challenged the consensus that general relativity has to be modified or “quantised” (e.g. loop quantum gravity) to be unified with quantum mechanics, by suggesting space-time may be classical, and that it is quantum mechanics which should be modified.[21] However, there is the third approach initiated by Landau and outlined above, namely that *general relativity is incomplete*. [7–12] The extension of general relativity which includes the reference frame

of the Observer (CIGR), results in a more complex structure for space-time (see above). The evidence for the photo-mirror effect,[16] shows that there is a connection between quantum mechanics and mirror space-time predicted by CIGR. Whilst this is clearly not yet a unified theory, it does suggest that it may well be possible to unify quantum mechanics with CIGR, since experiment is the final arbiter of truth.

This new theoretical framework is applied in the phenomenology section below, to understand the nature of matter in mirror space-time, and to show that there may be two different systems of charge quantisation, one in each space-time. This new physics is then applied to re-interpreting the experiments to detect the smallest electric charge. Historically this led to a dispute between Millikan and Ehrenhaft. We are not interested in history, but what Nature actually does, and so our approach is mainly experimental.

II. POSSIBLE NATURE OF MATTER IN MIRROR SPACE-TIME.

It is shown above that space-time is dual. Therefore there may be two systems of charge quantisation. For example, integral charge (ne) in normal space-time (eg electrons or protons), and fractional charges in mirror space-time for the following reasons. According to CIGR, massive particles such as neutrons and protons, should be mass dipoles. However nucleons are composite, and most of their mass comes from the gluons, which are massless. Therefore according to CIGR, gluons are not mass dipoles. Therefore they only exist in normal space-time where the strong interaction is observed, and so are excluded from the mirror sector where different forces may act. Quarks however have mass and so must be mass dipoles with the normal mass state being inside the hadron,[22, 23] and the negative pole (mirror quark) being in mirror space-time, where there are no gluons. Therefore mirror quarks are not bound into (mirror) hadrons. Therefore fractional electric charges may be detected in mirror space-time:

Hypothesis: Fractional electric charges can be observed in mirror space-time.

Therefore experiments which involve intense illumination which can reverse the direction of time, may provide evidence for fractional charges in mirror space-time, just as magnetic monopoles have been observed there.[13, 17–19] Three generations of quarks have been observed, which implies sub-structure, which has led to theories of preons.[24] Most preon models require a new force to bind them together into point-like quarks or leptons, which results in preons with high masses (tens of GeV). But there is no evidence for such a force in existing physics. However, if the preons are based in mirror space-time,

then this force could be undetectable in normal 4D space-time if its bosons are massless. Furthermore, if preons are located in mirror space-time, then their fractional charges may also be observed there.

We deduce from this that experiments to determine the minimum quantum of electric charge, will fall into two categories: those that are mainly sensitive to the first type of integer charge ne , and those which are more sensitive to the second type (fractional). Furthermore, a key difference between these two types of experiment is likely to be the level of illumination. Now let us examine the experimental evidence.

III. THE CHARGE OF THE ELECTRON

In 1897 J.J. Thomson at the Cavendish Laboratory determined that cathode rays are negatively charged, and have a large charge-to-mass ratio ($e/m = 7.7 \times 10^6$ esu).[25] This was the discovery of the electron. However, its mass and charge were unknown.

A number of physicists made determinations of the electron charge by a variety of methods in the early 1900s. However we are going to concentrate on two of them, Millikan and his oil drop experiment and Ehrenhaft, with his observations of "subelectrons" (i.e. particles with fractional electric charge), and the dispute which developed between them. On the face of it, Ehrenhaft was the "loser" when Millikan won the 1923 Nobel prize (for determining the charge on the electron and the photoelectric effect). However, physics should not be based upon history, but upon what Nature does. The problem at that time was that theory, namely atomic theory in single space-time, may have biased the results. Our approach is to avoid controversy, keep history to a minimum, and try to interpret the results in terms of the above new physics."

Despite this acceptance of Millikan's value for the charge of the electron by the physics community, Ehrenhaft went on writing about subelectrons into the 1940s. Furthermore, he reported observation of magnetic monopoles in 1930, which became even more controversial than subelectrons.[17] However as mentioned above, Mikhailov confirmed in considerable detail that Ehrenhaft had indeed observed Dirac monopoles, albeit in mirror space-time and not in normal space-time.[13, 19] *It thus seems only fair to give Ehrenhaft the benefit of the doubt and consider the possibility that he did observe "subelectrons" (i.e. fractionally charged particles), and investigate the physics of this.*

The dispute between Millikan and Ehrenhaft has been written about extensively mainly by historians of science. Niaz provides an overview of the four main appraisals.[26]

Holston has suggested that Millikan and Ehrenhaft had different “presuppositions”, and there is some evidence for that.[27] However we show below that they were in effect *doing different experiments, when the photo-mirror effect is taken into account*. Franklin gives a physicist’s appraisal of Millikan’s work based on his laboratory note books now at Caltech.[28] See also Barnes et al. who consider the difficulties of doing the oil drop experiment,[29] and Goodstein.[30] (Ehrenhaft’s note books appear to have been lost.)

The main results published by Millikan and Ehrenhaft are now summarised respectively, with emphasis on how they may be re-interpreted in light of the new physics above. Specifically we investigate whether the photo-mirror effect has biased searches for fractional charges, because this effect was not recognised nor allowed for at the time.

A. Millikan

In 1909 Millikan attended the meeting of the British Association for the Advancement of Science in Canada, where Rutherford presented his determination of the electron charge from alpha decay to be $e = 4.65 \times 10^{-10}$ esu.[31] Rutherford also mentioned Ehrenhaft’s initial result, based upon observations of positive and negative charges on particles of silver, of $e = 4.6 \times 10^{-10}$ esu, which provided confirmation.[32] These results appear to have played a key role in guiding Millikan’s work, in the sense that he focused on getting more precise results in approximate agreement.

After trying several methods,[33] Millikan abandoned water drops and substituted oil drops because this reduced evaporation. Furthermore, by allowing a single oil drop to fall under gravity, and then rise against gravity by means of an upwards electric field, and repeating this, he could follow an individual drop for an hour or more.

Millikan’s apparatus was fairly basic and functional, and is shown in figure 1.[34] It consisted of a condenser with horizontal plates (diameter 20 cm), the voltage across these could be varied; in a chamber whose gas pressure could be varied, the whole being surrounded by a constant temperature bath. There was a simple microscope to observe the motion of the drops, and an x-ray source to induce charges on them. In his Nobel acceptance speech he mentions some of the problems.

The equation of motion of a drop moving in an upwards electric field F is $m\ddot{x} = mg - K\dot{x} - QF$ where Q is the drop’s charge. From Stokes’ law $K = 6\pi a\mu$ where a is the drop’s radius and μ is the viscosity of air. In order to compensate for the particulate nature of air, Millikan replaced K by $K/(1+b/pa)$, where p is the air pressure, and b is

FIG. 1: Millikan's apparatus. High grade watch-oil droplets from the atomiser A blown by a puff of air (dried and cleaned) through r , enter the condenser MN , are illuminated by light from an arc (on left, not shown) filtered through a trough of water w and cupric chloride d to remove heat rays. The temperature was held constant to within 0.2 degrees by oil-bath G . The charge p on a drop could be changed by x-rays X via window g . The pressure was varied from 13 to 76 cm and measured to 0.1 mm by the manometer m . The optical system was a microscope with an objective of 30 mm and magnification of 25 diameters. The cross-hair distance was 1.0220 cm and the velocities were determined by a printing chronograph.

a parameter determined by experiment. All the measurements were made at terminal velocities so that $\ddot{x} = 0$, whence:

$$Q = \frac{mg}{F} \left[\frac{v_f + v_g}{v_g} \right] \quad (3)$$

Where v_f and v_g are the terminal velocities with and without the field F respectively. The mass m , after allowing for the buoyancy effect of the air, can be replaced by a using $m = (4/3)\pi a^3(\sigma - \rho)$, where σ and ρ are the density of oil and air respectively. Furthermore, a can be replaced by μ using Stokes' law, and the velocities v_f and v_g replaced by the ratios of the distance d between crosshairs, and the stop-watch times of rise t_f and fall t_g respectively. These give:

$$Q = ne = 9\pi d \sqrt{\frac{2}{g}} \frac{1}{F} \left(\frac{\mu^3}{(\sigma - \rho)(1 + b/pa)^3} \right)^{1/2} \times \left[\sqrt{v_g} \left(\frac{1}{t_f} + \frac{1}{t_g} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where the first equality assumes that the charge is integral. This can be reduced to:

$$e = \frac{A}{F} \cdot B(T) \cdot \sqrt{v_g} \cdot C'(n, t) \quad \text{where} \quad C'(n, t) = \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{1}{t_f} + \frac{1}{t_g} \right) \quad (5)$$

The number of charges n on a drop can be 1 to 100 or more. It can be difficult to determine the exact number of charges when n is high. However, it is quite common for the charge on a drop to change by a small amount Δn , usually by just 1 or 2, during repeated measurements of one drop. When this occurs on a falling drop, it is possible to calculate the change in charge from the rise times t_f before and after t'_f , so that

$$\Delta Q = (\Delta n)e = 9\pi d \sqrt{\frac{2}{g}} \frac{1}{F} \left(\frac{\mu^3}{(\sigma - \rho)(1 + b/pa)^3} \right)^{1/2} \times \left[\sqrt{v_g} \left(\frac{1}{t_f} - \frac{1}{t'_f} \right) \right] \quad (6)$$

So that:

$$e = \frac{A}{F} \cdot B(T) \cdot \sqrt{v_g} \cdot D'(\Delta n, t) \quad \text{where} \quad D'(\Delta n, t) = \frac{1}{\Delta n} \left(\frac{1}{t_f} - \frac{1}{t'_f} \right) \quad (7)$$

In the actual experiment it is often easier to determine $D'(\Delta n, t)$ first, and then determine $C'(n, t)$. If the two disagree, the event is not self-consistent and Millikan tended to reject such events. However, this becomes more complicated if there are fractional charges - see below.

In his 1911 results, Millikan stated that he had observed one to two thousand changes in charge, and each time it was in units of $e = 4.891 \times 10^{-10}$ esu with a precision of about 0.2 percent, plus some additional uncertainty from the viscosity of air.[35]

He then made improvements to the optical system; determined a better value for the viscosity of air, which changes the correction parameter in Stokes' law; and measured the distance between the crosshairs more precisely. He presented his final result in 1913.[36] Based on 58 drops observed in a 60 day period, and without omitting any drops (but see below), he determined that $e = (4.774 \pm 0.009) \times 10^{-10}$ esu. This is lower than his 1911 result because of the improvements in his method. It differs from the more modern value of $e = (4.8032068 \pm 0.0000015) \times 10^{-10}$ esu in part because of a difference in the viscosity of air.

However, when one has access to his laboratory notebooks, a different picture emerges. Franklin found that of the total 175 drops in the notebooks, 117 were excluded, some for

valid reasons (such as the apparatus was not working properly), but many for no reason at all, see Franklin and Niaz for details.[26, 28] Not only did Millikan exclude drops, but he also selected drops to improve the statistical accuracy of his result.[28] Instead of plotting the distribution of charge and selecting all the drops within a certain range and then averaging these, he basically "cherry-picked" the drops he included in his final result. Thus Millikan's data analysis techniques are unsatisfactory. *However, this is not the focus of this paper, because we are looking for new physics.*

B. Ehrenhaft

Although Ehrenhaft was younger than Millikan, he was already quite well-established in Vienna, and had more sophisticated apparatus. His thesis experiment in 1903 was on the optical properties of metal colloids.[37] He modified this sensitive apparatus to study the Brownian motion of silver particles in air, which provided a more stringent test of the atomic hypothesis due to the greater mean free path.[38] It was this apparatus with a horizontal electric field, which required measurements on two drops (one without the electric field and one with), which he used to determine the value of e which confirmed Rutherford's result given above.[32]

He then introduced a condenser (diameter 8 mm) with a vertical electric field strong enough to cause the particles to rise against gravitation (similar to Millikan). He used an arc to produce platinum and silver particles, and reported results of 22 measurements in the range 7.53×10^{-10} esu down to 1.38×10^{-10} esu (0.29e).[39] He denied that these results were due to inadequacies of the method, and concluded that if there is an elementary electrical charge, *it must be smaller than that of the electron*. This is the first observation of fractional electric charges. He introduced the term "sub-electron" in his next paper in 1910.[40] The problem is that this result challenged the Atomic Theory then being established (we show below that it does not, when the new physics is taken into account).

Ehrenhaft then reported fractional charges in a number of papers over the next 30 years.[41, 42] This produced a strong criticism from Millikan,[43] and vigorous responses from Ehrenhaft and his students Zerner and Konstantinowsky.[42, 44] In fact Millikan's Nobel Prize was delayed by this dispute until 1923. But this is not our focus.

In Vienna, the approach to fundamental physics tends to include some philosophy[45] Ehrenhaft did not accept that the atomic hypothesis was proven, and argued that Mil-

FIG. 2: The apparatus Ehrenhaft used to study photophoresis, showing the complex optical arrangements. More details are given in the references.[46]

likan's approach was circular reasoning (*petitio principii*). So Ehrenhaft set out to determine the *smallest* quantum of charge, because if there were fractional charges, then the atomic theory was possibly in doubt. It is not just that their objectives were different, but their experimental setups were also significantly different.

Ehrenhaft's apparatus was optically quite complex, as shown in figure 2,[46] in part because he had originally developed it to study colloids. He also had ready access to German optical systems, and later incorporated an ultra-microscope, which can observe particles smaller than the optical limit. At various times he also used three different types of condenser: a small one (8 mm), a larger one closer in size to that of Millikan, and a fairly small high pressure one, which are shown here.[47] However, one of the key differences was that most of the time, Ehrenhaft used the smaller condenser only 8 mm in diameter, whereas that of Millikan was 25 times larger. This had two important consequences:

Firstly Ehrenhaft could focus much more intense illumination into such a small volume. In fact the illumination was from both sides (left and right), and was so intense that he had to pass it through solutions of Mohr's salt to absorb the excess heat.

Secondly, the small condenser enabled him to use an objective lens with a smaller focal length and a larger numerical aperture, so that he could observe smaller particles

than Millikan, even in the submicroscopic range of 1 to 3×10^{-5} cm. In fact Ehrenhaft estimates that the smallest particle Millikan could observe in principle would be about 3×10^{-5} cm, and he claims that in practice Millikan left out drops smaller than 9×10^{-5} cm.[48] This is significant because Ehrenhaft reported that *the smaller particles tend to have fractional charges on them*. Millikan ridiculed this observation as absurd! We offer an explanation for this below.

Ehrenhaft's critics maintained his technique was faulty in several different ways, such as that the particles were not spherical, the size was wrong, the density different from the bulk material, etc. Ehrenhaft set out to overcome some of those objections, using special techniques he presented in his 1941 paper (when he was a refugee in New York).[42] He first made measurements in the normal way described above, on solid spheres of red amorphous selenium (because solids do not evaporate nor lose their sphericity, as liquid drops can), to determine their charge. He then succeeded in precipitating the particle just measured, onto a quartz plate, and then used special techniques to determine its sphericity and diameter ($< 3 \times 10^{-5}$ cm), and confirmed the density at high pressure using Stokes' law - see his paper for details.[42] He then repeated these operations on the next particle.

In this way, he managed to make this complete set of delicate measurements on 6 particles. So there were no uncertainties for these. The results are shown in the upper histogram in figure 3. Three of which have approximately the known charge of the electron, one is about twice that charge, and two are about $2/3e$. He compares these with higher statistics measurements made some 20 years earlier (shown in the lower histogram in figure 3) which also has a peak around $2/3e$. Ehrenhaft's measured conclusion in 1941 is that he had observed charges *as small as one tenth of the electronic charge*. [41, 42]

Perl et al. have made a survey of searches for fractionally charged particles, and state they found no evidence in over 50 years of research.[49] However, they did not point out that whilst some studies rule out quarks with a minimum charge of $e/3$, they do not rule out preons with charges of $e/9$ or less. For example, Ziocck did not find any evidence for charges greater than $0.15e$, but could not rule out charges less than this.[50] Furthermore, their treatment of Ehrenhaft is not completely fair. They describe him as "eccentric", and write that he "claimed to have found particles with charges that were a fraction of e - findings that were never confirmed". So let us see whether they were confirmed or not.

FIG. 3: Some of Ehrenhaft's data. The abscissa is charge in units of 10^{-10} esu, and the ordinate is counts for two sets of data. The upper curve (solid) shows the results of measuring 6 particles at high gas pressure, then precipitating them onto a quartz plate to remove them from the condenser, and then micro-photographing them in such a way as to determine directly their sphericity, size and density. These complex operations are very delicate and particles easily get lost - hence only six completed all the operations. 3 of the particles have the charge e of the electron, one is greater, and 2 are less than e by amounts significantly larger than the experimental errors. The minimum charge of these 6 particles was $3.2 \cdot 10^{-10}$ esu. The lower curve (open) with higher statistics, was made by a colleague using red Se spheres, and clearly shows a peak around $2e/3$ with a minimum charge of $2 \cdot 10^{-10}$ esu which is about $4e/9$.

C. Preliminary Corroboration of Ehrenhaft

Ehrenhaft states that a number of other experimenters have corroborated his results.[51] Millikan dismissed these as being students or collaborators, which is only partly true. Physicists (mainly in Austria and Germany) who used Ehrenhaft's method and measured sufficiently small particles, found charges substantially below $e = 4.77 \times 10^{-10}$ esu, according to Daecke. The problem was that one group regarded the sub-electrons as real, whilst others that they were produced by a range of erroneous techniques. To solve this problem, Daecke of Hamburg made a statistical analysis of some independent results.[52]

The data he used came from M. König, who studied minute drops of mercury in air and in carbon dioxide.[53] He also used observations made by E. Radel, also of mercury in air.[54] He selected mercury data because the drops are spherical. Furthermore, their high reflectivity enabled observation to be made on small drops, whose fractional charge was often significantly below $e = 4.77 \times 10^{-10}$ esu. König found this occurred for drops with radius $r < 1.2 \times 10^{-5}$ cm, and Radel for $r < 0.9 \times 10^{-5}$ cm, both for mercury in air. Daecke then applied a cyclical statistical technique developed by R. v. Mises to determine integers, which he first applied to atomic weights.[55] This technique requires

Table 1: Evidence for Fractional Charges in Millikan's Data

$(1/t_f+1/t_g)$	$/n = C'$	$/(n - 0.1) = C'$	$/(n - 1/9) = C'$
0.075872	$/11 = 0.006897$	$/10.9 = 0.006961$	$/10.889 = 0.006968$
0.09001	$/13 = 0.006924$	$/12.9 = 0.006978$	$/12.889 = 0.006983$
0.09723	$/14 = 0.006945$	$/13.9 = 0.006995$	$/13.889 = 0.007001$
mean C'	0.006922	0.006978	0.006984
D'	0.006992	0.006992	0.006992
$\Delta = C' - D'$	-0.000070	-0.000014	-0.000008

that the charges observed are integral multiples of some fundamental charge (e.g. 0.50×10^{-10} esu = $e/9.5$). He found the two most prominent peaks to occur at $e/19$ and $e/9$, with a number of minor peaks. (We discuss the peak at $e/19$ in more detail below.) Daecke concluded "The assumption that the sub-electrons may be represented in the form me/n , where n is not large and $m < n$, possesses greater probability than any other assumption". So there is independent experimental and statistical evidence for fractional electric charges.

Under normal circumstances, this would be enough to consider Perl et al. to be wrong. However, there is still the dispute with Millikan, and he won the Nobel Prize.

D. Corroboration from Millikan

Whilst the data given below is not as good as Mikhailov's magnetic monopole results, there is some evidence *in Millikan's own papers and note books*, which support Ehrenhaft:

1. In 1910 Millikan reported "I have discarded one uncertain and unduplicated observation apparently on a singly charged drop, which gave a value of the charge on the drop some 30 per cent lower than the final value of e .[33] He explained this away, as being due to the rapid evaporation of the water droplet being observed. But was it? This is one possible fractional charge.

2. Holton on pages 209-210 draws attention to the second drop Millikan measured on 15 March 1912. This was a heavy drop which gave inconsistent results (i.e. $C' \neq D'$), so Millikan wrote in his note book "Error high will not use".[27] It seems that he moved on to measure the next drop. However Holton points out that these measurements are consistent *if the charges are fractional*, in this case of about $0.1e$.

We now recalculate this event, using Millikan's data quoted by Holton, allowing also for charges of $e/9$. Table 1 above shows the results for $Q = ne$; $Q = (n-0.1)e$ and $Q = (n-1/9)e$. Three data points for one (Millikan) drop is not an experiment. But it is interesting to note that a fractional charge of $e/9$ gives the most consistent result, because this is in agreement with the result found by Daecke above. Furthermore, it agrees with Ehrenhaft's observation that the minimum fractional charge is $0.1e$, within the errors).[41, 42] *So this event seems to be one valid fractional charge in Millikan's data.* Thus Millikan's focus on integer charges forced him to discard valid data for fractional charges!

This event is not just evidence for *Millikan's biased methodology*, but also evidence (from Millikan's data) *that his reasoning was circular*, as Ehrenhaft claimed. In effect, Millikan won the Nobel Prize because he *confirmed the atomic theory*, whilst Ehrenhaft lost because there was *no theory of fractional electric charges nor the duality of space-time*. We have discussed how theory is sometimes biased against experiment in a separate paper.[13]

3. Franklin has reanalyzed Millikan's data and finds three anomalous drops. The first on 20 January 1912 is completely inconsistent, does not make sense, and is rejected. The other two are *consistent with fractional charges*. He obtains a corrected value of $e = 1.915 \times 10^{-10}$ esu ($0.40e$) for the fourth drop on 7 March 1912, and $e = 2.810 \times 10^{-10}$ esu ($0.59e$) for the second drop on 16 April 1912. However, Franklin says these are not evidence for free quarks, *because both the charges on these drops and the changes in charges are fractional*. He writes "It would indeed be remarkable if the fractional changes in charge... occurred only on drops which were themselves fractionally charged".[28]

However, this can be understood if the drop has been switched into the mirror state. Then some or all of the atoms would be in mirror space-time, and a particle leaving could be fractionally charged (e.g. $e/9$) and leave behind a fractionally charged state (e.g. $2e/9$). The point is that *once one understands that light can switch the direction of time (locally), fractionally charged particles would not be uncommon. Thus these two events are evidence for fractional charges.*

4. In the 1970s when the quark model predicted fractional charges, physicists tried to detect free quarks, and indeed claims were made that fractional charges were observed on niobium spheres.[56] Following this, Fairbank and Franklin re-analyzed Millikan's original data (but not Ehrenhaft's) using modern methods, to see if he had observed fractional

charges on oil drops. They appear to have rejected the two anomalous events mentioned in point 3 above, even though these are clearcut evidence. They then conclude “Millikan’s original data gives strong evidence for charge quantisation and no convincing evidence for fractional residual charge, although two events [out of 61] are consistent with such an interpretation”. [57] So there are two more possible fractionally charged events, making a total of at least 3 and possibly up to 6 in Millikan’s data. Thus Millikan did observe fractional charges, *but at a lower rate than Ehrenhaft.*

So in addition to corroboration by König and Radel and Daecke’s statistical analysis, *there is partial corroboration from Millikan’s data.* So Perl et al. appear to be wrong. Now let us look for the new physics.

E. Interpretation of above Experiments

1. We have seen above that Ehrenhaft used a set-up which was optically more sophisticated than Millikan’s. (So too did König and Radel because they could also observe sub-microscopic particles.) Furthermore, his principle condenser was smaller (by a factor of 25) than Millikan’s and so the light was focused (from two sides) into a smaller volume, thereby increasing its intensity. In fact Ehrenhaft advises turning the illumination level down. [42] Furthermore he used similar apparatus to discover magnetic monopoles, which also requires intense illumination (Mikhailov used a laser with up to 1kW per cm² to detect monopoles). So whilst it is not quantified, *there is evidence that Ehrenhaft (and probably König and Radel) employed higher levels of illumination than Millikan.*

2. Furthermore, Millikan’s oil drops were made from clock oil, which is normally *transparent*. As a result, photons would tend to pass *through* them without interacting, whereas the particles used by Ehrenhaft (red amorphous Selenium, silver, platinum) are *opaque* to light, as are mercury drops used by König and Radel. *Therefore, photons are more likely to interact with them, and switch part or all of these particles into the mirror-world state via the photo-mirror effect, thereby revealing fractional charges there.*

3. Ehrenhaft, König and Radel all observed that *smaller* particles tended to have fractional charges. The cross-section for photons of an opaque particle of radius a goes as πa^2 . Therefore larger drops would tend to interact with more photons and have more domains switched into mirror space-time by photons, so that the net fractional charge revealed is more likely to exceed *unity* e . In this case it would be difficult to get a clear observation of the actual fractional charge(s), because the total charge would be made

up from several different unity and/or fractional charges, with a total $Q > e$. However, smaller drops would interact with fewer photons, maybe only 1 or 2, so that the net fractional charge revealed is more likely to be $Q < e$. *Therefore one is more likely to observe fractional charges on smaller drops*, as detected. In fact one is more likely to observe the minimum fractional charge in this way. NB This only makes sense if the fractional charges, instead of being rare, are being revealed by the photo-mirror effect switching the direction of time.

These three factors, whilst not conclusive, could explain why Ehrenhaft and others observed more fractionally charged particles than Millikan's 3 to 6 drops. They are in effect *different experiments*, when the photo-mirror effect is taken into account. These results also support the hypothesis that (mirror) quarks are located in mirror space-time, but can be revealed by the photo-mirror effect.

Ehrenhaft provides evidence that the smallest charge is about $0.1e$. Daecke's statistical analysis supports this with a strong peak at $e/9$. Millikan supports this with one drop which gives evidence for charge $e/9$.

F. Preons

There is evidence above for particles with charges $e/3$ and $2e/3$ in mirror space-time. These could be (mirror) quarks or preons, depending on the model. However, the above data suggest that the minimum charge is $0.1e$ to $e/9$, which cannot be due to quarks. Furthermore it rules out most preon models which have a minimum charge of $e/3$.

Before we draw conclusions, we need to discuss the peak Daecke found at $e/19$. This could be some sort of instrumental effect. Or it could be an aberration produced by the peculiar statistical technique used (e.g. that the minimum charge assumed was 0.50×10^{-10} esu = $e/9.5$). Or it could be physically real. For example, preon models tend to predict charges of e/n and $2e/n$, where n is 3 or 9. If n is 18, then there would be preons with charges $e/18$ and $e/9$, in which case the peak at $e/19$ could be physically real, but with a small error in determining its correct value. Since no one else reported charges of $e/19$ (or $e/18$), it could be some kind of error. *However, if the minimum charge is $e/9$, then one would expect there to be a charge of $2e/9$. But there is no evidence for a charge of $0.22e$* So may be the minimum charge in mirror space-time really is $e/19$ (or $e/18$). People repeating these experiments, need to investigate this further, and theoreticians need to investigate the feasibility of preon theories with charges of $e/18$ and $e/9$.

Subject to the above condition, we conclude that Ehrenhaft's, Daecke's and Millikan's results support the existence of preons, but with a charge of $e/9$. The author has found two preon models with charges of $e/9$. They both predict quark masses. However, the preon model due to Bevelacqua, predicts the up quark mass to be $336 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, whereas experimental values are in the range 1.9 to $5.4 \text{ MeV}/c^2$, so he is off by a factor of order 90.[58] However, he predicts that the six preons in his model have masses 27.1 , 26.9 , 27.8 , 28.8 , 32.7 , and $98.3 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ respectively. Yershov's approach is based upon a dual space-time. His model predicts the quark and lepton masses, without using input parameters, with an accuracy of 0.5% .[59], which is impressive. But his preons have mass $m_e/9$ ($0.057 \text{ MeV}/c^2$) and to get the required mass, an up quark contains 78 such preons and the d quark 123 preons. This is quite a complex theory - perhaps a bit contrived.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Many physicists think that claims of observation of fractional electric charges are false, and this may be the case. The alternative possibility is that the theoretical framework for these experiments was wrong, which is the approach taken here. If the former is correct, the results will be the occasional random event. However, if the latter is correct, there will be correlations between the methods, results and this new physics.

We have shown that Millikan and Ehrenhaft (and others) had different objectives, the former to determine the charge on the electron, and the latter to determine the minimum quantum of charge. There is evidence that Millikan was so focused on detecting integral charge (*ne*) that he rejected fractional charge when he detected it (see table 1). This evidence supports Ehrenhaft's observation that Millikan's reasoning was circular (*petitio principii*) in favour of the atomic hypothesis (supported by the single space-time assumption).

In fact there is evidence presented above, for fractionally charged particles in the data of Ehrenhaft, König and Radel, and also in that of Millikan, although at a lower rate. We have shown that Ehrenhaft and Millikan *were doing physically different experiments, when optics and the photo-mirror effect are allowed for*. Ehrenhaft, König and Radel used *opaque* particles, superior optics and probably higher levels of illumination, which meant that photons interacted at higher rates to reveal (and so observe) more fractionally charged particles, via the photo-mirror effect, because more photons will interact with opaque particles. Millikan had lower light levels and used *transparent* drops (clock oil),

which most photons would traverse without interacting, so that fewer fractionally charged particles were revealed by the photo-mirror effect. Never-the-less there are at least 3 and possibly up to 6 fractionally charged candidates in Millikan's work, thereby providing some corroboration.

The minimum charge observed by Ehrenhaft was $0.1e$ and that by one of Millikan's drops was $e/9$. Daecke's statistical analysis also found charges of $e/9$ (although his minimum was $e/19 \simeq e/18?$). These results rule out preon models with a minimum charge of $e/3$, but support those with a charge of $e/9$. The preon model by Yershov based in dual space-time, also has this minimum charge $e/9$, and predicts the quark and lepton masses to within 0.5%, but it is complex, and there was no evidence for a charge of $2e/9$. So the correct preon theory may have preons with charges of $e/18$ and $e/9$.

This correlation between the sophistication of optics, level of illumination, opaqueness of the target drops, and the number of fractional charges observed, suggests that the photo-mirror effect plays a role in these experiments, which was not understood at the time. Furthermore the fact that the one fractional drop observed by Millikan which the author has data on, is best fitted by a charge of $e/9$ in agreement with the statistical analysis by Daecke of König and Radel's data, is not exactly random. Whilst 1 event is not an experiment, there is a correlation here which needs to be investigated further.

A. New Experiments

Once the role of the photo-mirror effect is understood, it becomes possible to study fractional charges with more precision. Not only can Ehrenhaft's experiments be repeated with more control over illumination to determine the fractional charges more precisely, but new experiments could be devised to measure other properties of (mirror) quarks and preons, in particular preon charges. Of particular interest would be to see if one can switch individual particles (e.g. protons) into the mirror world state, using a high enough intensity of light. Such experiments could create preon matter to be studied in the laboratory. Preon spectroscopy may be possible.

B. A New Approach to Unification

Currently the two main approaches to unification are either to modify general relativity (e.g. loop quantum gravity) or to modify quantum mechanics, so the two may

be unified.[21] The third approach initiated by Landau and outlined above, is that *general relativity is incomplete, because it does not correct for the reference frame of the Observer.*[7]

The extension of general relativity which includes the Observer (CIGR), results in a more complex structure for space-time, with a second time dimension, directed from the future to the past, in mirror space-time This is separated from normal space-time by a membrane.[8–12] We have found experimental evidence for mirror space-time and its second time dimension, and for the membrane.[16] There is also evidence for new states of matter in mirror space-time, such as magnetic monopoles,[13] and for quarks and preons given above. In separate experiments, we have also presented evidence for a new type of (non-electromagnetic) radiation in sunlight, possibly a new force of nature, which lowers entropy levels which persist.[20] We deduce that this new type of solar radiation is also in the mirror sector because it produces ordered structures which persist.

These results provide examples of the new low energy phenomena which occur in mirror space-time beyond the standard model. Therefore the hypothesis is made that mirror space-time is the physical basis for the hidden sector of a new type of unified theory based upon CIGR and quantum mechanics, which has yet to be formulated mathematically. The evidence for the photo-mirror effect,[16] shows that there is a connection between quantum mechanics (Brittin and Gamow effect) and mirror space-time predicted by CIGR. Whilst this is clearly not yet a unified theory, it does suggest that it may well be possible to unify quantum mechanics with CIGR, since experiment is the final arbiter of truth.

This approach opens up new experimental methods for studying quarks and preons, and possibly dark matter (see appendix below). It also opens up new theoretical approaches, especially to unification, since evidence for the photo-mirror effect is evidence for the unification of CIGR with quantum mechanics. A key detail which may be significant is that the Observer occurs in both theories, in CIGR which corrects for the Observer's reference frame, and in quantum mechanics where the Observer collapses the wave function.

V. GLOSSARY

CIGR Borissova and Rabounski refer to their extension of general relativity as the “chronometric invariant formalism of general relativity”. However, this is a major extension of general relativity from 4 dimensions (3,1) to 5D (3,2). It describes a more

complex Universe and so is more than just a formalism but a theory in its own right and so deserves its own name. In the absence of such a name, the author refers to it as “chronometric invariant general relativity” (CIGR). However this is clumsy and inelegant, and is only intended until a new name is chosen. Strictly speaking the authors should choose the name, or the physics community at large. Words are important.[60]

VI. LIMITATIONS

The author is an experimentalist and so the reasoning is from experimental evidence upwards, rather than mathematical principles downwards. Better data is needed, and the theory needs to be properly developed.

Data Availability Statement: No Data is associated with this manuscript.

AppendixA: Dark Matter

The conjecture is made that preons, revealed by the photo-mirror effect, are dark matter. Stars are sources of vast amounts of visible light, which would interact with the normal matter in the space around them and could switch some of that into the mirror-world state. Therefore the amount of dark matter is likely to be highest where the illumination is greatest. There is some evidence for this.[61] Furthermore, it has been found that in clusters of galaxies and larger structures on scales above $300h^{-1}\text{kpc}$, dark matter mass follows light on all scales with a nearly constant mass-to-light ratio $M_{DM}/L = \text{const.}$ [62]

The dark matter density $\Omega_c = 0.259 \pm 0.006$ is about 5.3 times the baryon density $\Omega_b = 0.0486 \pm 0.001$. [63] However, preon models often predict preon masses to be tens of GeV/c^2 or more. For example Bevelacqua’s model above predicts that a proton consisting of two up quarks and a down quark contains 9 preons with a total mass of $243 \text{ GeV}/c^2$ when all are liberated. This would require only about 2% of the baryons to be converted into such preons to explain Ω_c .

Preons cannot form atoms and produce atomic spectra, as long as they are in mirror space-time. Furthermore, they are in effect “chameleons” because they will revert to normal hadrons if the entropy level is raised, according to equation (2). Preons are expected to be stable, because they are the building blocks of matter. Most importantly, preons are non-baryonic constituents of normal matter. So one may not need to invent a new type of particle to explain most of the mass in the universe.

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- [1] T.D.Lee and C.N. Yang, *Phys. Rev.* **104** (1956) 254; J.W. Ciu et al. [arXiv: hep-ph/1293.0968].
- [2] L. Boyle, M. Teuscher and N. Turok, [arXiv:2208.10396 hep-ph].
- [3] J. Barbour, T.A. Koslowski and F. Mercati, [arXiv:1604.03956 gr-qc]
- [4] S.P. Martin, "A Supersymmetry Primer", [arXiv:hep-ph/9709356]
- [5] P. Marquet, "Twin Universes Confirmed by General Relativity", *Progress in Physics*, 2022 **v18**, issue 1, 89-94.
- [6] J. Jaeckel and A. Ringwald, *Ann. Rev. Nucl. Part. Sci.* **60**, 405 (2010).
- [7] Landau L. D. and Lifshitz E. M. *The classical theory of fields*, (GITTL, Moscow, 1939, see 4th final edition, Butterworth-Heinemann, 1980).
- [8] A.L. Zelmanov, "Chronometric invariants and the accompanying frames of reference in the General Theory of Relativity", *Soviet Physics Doklady*, 1956, **vol 1**, 227-230.
- [9] A.L. Zelmanov, *Chronometric Invariants*, Translation of 1944 Dissertation, CERN, EXT-2004-117.
- [10] C. Cattaneo, *Nuov. Cim.* **10** (1958) pp 318-337; *ibid* **11** (1959) pp 733-735; *ibid* **13** (1959) pp 237-240.
- [11] D. Rabounski and L. Borissova, *Particles Here and Beyond the Mirror*, 4th Ed. (New Scientific Frontiers, London, 2023, and from progress-in-physics.com).
- [12] L. Borissova and D. Rabounski, *Fields, Vacuum and the Mirror Universe*, 3rd Ed. (New Scientific Frontiers, London, 2023, and from progress-in-physics.com) Chapters 1 and 6; CERN, EXT-2003-025, 1st Ed.
- [13] R.J. Ellis, "I: Evidence for Phenomena, including Magnetic Monopoles, Beyond 4-D Space-Time and Theory Thereof", *Progress in Physics* 2024 **20**, issue 2, 127-134; [arXiv:2207.04916].
- [14] W. Brittin and G. Gamow, "Negative Entropy and Photosynthesis". *Proc. of the Nat. Acad. of Sciences*, **47** (1961) 724.
- [15] A. S. Eddington, *The Nature of the Physical World*, (Cambridge University Press, 1928).
- [16] R.J. Ellis, "II: Preliminary Evidence for a Second Time Dimension Directed from the Future to the Past, and for Unification", *Progress in Physics* 2024 **20**, issue 2, 135-148; doi:10.5281/zenodo.7347637.

- [17] F. Ehrenhaft, *Phys. Zeitschr.* **31**, 478 (1930).
- [18] V.F. Mikhailov, "On Interpretation of the Magnetic Charge Effect on Ferromagnetic Aerosols", *Preprint HEPI 88-05*, Kazakh Academy of Sciences, Alma-Ata, USSR (1988) see figure 2.
- [19] V.F. Mikhailov, "Experimental Detection of Dirac's Magnetic Charge? ", *J. Phys. D: Applied Physics*, **29** (1996) 801-804.
- [20] R.J. Ellis, "III: Preliminary Evidence for a New Type of Radiation in Sunlight", doi:10.5281/zenodo.7347703.
- [21] J. Oppenheim, "A postquantum theory of classical gravity", *PhysRevX*, **13(4)**, 041040 (2023); [arXiv:1811.03116].
- [22] C. Llewellyn-Smith, "From concrete quarks to QCD: a personal perspective", *Eur. Phys. J. H* (2023) 48:13.
- [23] V.A. Petrov, "The idea of quarks: towards restoring of historical justice", [arXiv.org/pdf/2001.04843].
- [24] C.S. Kalman, "Why quarks cannot be fundamental particles" *Nuclear Physics B (Proceedings Supplements)*, 2005, Elsevier; [arXiv: hep-ph/0411313].
- [25] J.J. Thomson, *Phil. Mag.* **44**, (1897) pp. 293-316.
- [26] M. Niaz, "An Appraisal of the Controversial Nature of the Oil Drop Experiment: Is Closure Possible? " *Brit. J. Phil. Sci.* **56** (2005) 681-702.
- [27] G Holton, "Subelectrons, Presuppositions, and the Millikan-Ehrenhaft Dispute", *Hist. Stud. in Phys. Sci.*, **9** (1978) pp. 162-324
- [28] A D Franklin, "Millikan's Published and Unpublished Data on Oil Drops", *Hist. Stud. in Phys. Sci.*, **11** (1981) pp. 185-201.
- [29] B. Barnes, D. Bloor and J. Henry, *Scientific Knowledge: A Sociologic Analysis*, (University of Chicago Press, IL. 1996).
- [30] D. Goodstein, "In Defence of Robert Andrews Millikan", *American Scientist*, **89** (2001) pp. 54-60.
- [31] E. Rutherford, "Address to the Mathematical and Physical Science Section", *Report of the 79 Meeting of the Brit. Ass. for Adv. of Science, Winnipeg, Canada*, (London: Murray, 1909) pp. 373-385.
- [32] F. Ehrenhaft, *Physikalische Zeitschrift*, **10** (1909) pp. 308-310.
- [33] R. A. Millikan, *Phil. Mag.* **19** (1910) pp. 209-228, note 6 p 220.

- [34] R. A. Millikan, *Proc. Nat. Acad. of Sci.* **3** (1917) 231.
- [35] R. A. Millikan, *Phys. Rev.* **32** (1911) 349.
- [36] R. A. Millikan, *Phys. Rev.* **2** (1913) 109-143
- [37] F. Ehrenhaft, *Annalen der Physik*, **II** (1903) 489.
- [38] F. Ehrenhaft, *Wiener Ber.(IIa)* **116** (1907) 1175.
- [39] F. Ehrenhaft, *Anzeiger Akad. Wiss. (Vienna)* **10** (1910) 118-119.
- [40] F. Ehrenhaft, *Anzeiger Akad. Wiss. (Vienna)* **13** (1910) 215.
- [41] F. Ehrenhaft, *Wiener Akad. Anzeiger 21, IV, 1910*; W.A.A. 12, V, 910; W.A.A. 4, XII, 1913; W. A. A. 19, II, 1914; Wiener Berichte (IIa) 119, 815, 1910; W.B.(IIa) 123, 53, 1914; Physikal Zeitschrift. 11, 619, 1910; P.Z. 11, 940, 1910; P.Z. 12, 94, 1911; P.Z. 12, 261, 1911; P.Z. 15, 952, 1914; P.Z. 16, 227, 1915; P.Z. 18, 352, 1917; Verhandl. d. deutschen Phys. Ges. 15, 1187, 1913; *ibid* 1350.
- [42] F. Ehrenhaft, *Phil. of Science*, **8** (1941) pp. 403-457.
- [43] R. A. Millikan, *Phys. Rev.* **8** (1916) 595.
- [44] F. Ehrenhaft, *Annalen der Physik*, **44** (1914) pp. 657-700; F. Zerner, *Physikalische Zeitschrift*, **16** (1915), 19-13; D. Konstantinowsky, *Annalen der Physik*, **46** (1915) 261-297.
- [45] F. Del Santo and E. Schwarzahns, "Philosophysics at the University of Vienna", *Phys. Perspect.* **24** (2022) 125-153.
- [46] F. Ehrenhaft, *Annalen d. Physik* **56** (1918) 81; *Phil. of Science*, **8** (1941) p 409
- [47] F. Ehrenhaft, *Phil. of Science*, **8** (1941), figure 1, p. 409.
- [48] F. Ehrenhaft, *Phil. of Science*, **8** (1941) p. 442.
- [49] M. L. Perl et al. *Ann. Rev. Nucl. Part. Sci.* **59** (2009) 47.
- [50] D. Liebowitz, M. Binder and K.O.H. Ziock, *Phys. Rev. Letts.* **50**(21) (1983) 1640.
- [51] F. Ehrenhaft, *Phil. of Science*, **8** (1941) see 14 references on p. 405.
- [52] H. Daecke, *Lond. Ed. and Dub. Phil. Mag. and J. of Science*, **50** (1925) pp. 637-644; *Physikal. Zeitschr.* **25**, 624 (1924); *Zeitschr. f. Physik*, **31**, 552 (1925) and **36**, 143 (1926).
- [53] M. König, *Zeitschr. f. Phys.* **xi** (1922) pp. 253-259.
- [54] E. Radcl, *Zeitschr. f. Phys.* **iii** (1920) pp. 63-68.
- [55] R. v. Mises, *Phys. Zeitschr.* **xix** (1918) pp. 490-500.
- [56] G. S. LaRue et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **46** (1981) 967.
- [57] Q. M. Fairbank. *Am. J. Phys.* **80**(5) (1982) 394.
- [58] J.J. Bevelacqua, *Nucl. and Part. Phys.* **9** (2019) pp 1-4.

- [59] V.N. Yershov, [arXiv:physics/0207120v9; hep-ph/0207132v7; physics/0609185].
- [60] V.L. Telegdi, private communication.
- [61] D. Coe et al, *AstroPhys. J.* **723** (2010) 1678.
- [62] N.A. Bahcall and A. Kulier, *Mon. Not. R. Astro. Soc.* **439** (2014) 2505.
- [63] Planck Collaboration, "Planck 2015 Results. XIII. Cosmological Parameters", *Astron. Astroph.* **594**(13) (2016) A13, calculated from p. 32, table 4, last column; [arXiv:1502.01589].